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Curricular Reforms at Different Levels of Teacher Education as per NCTE Regulations-2014 <i>Dr. M. C. Yarriswamy and Shivakumar G. M.</i>	224
A Correlational Study of Problem Solving Ability, Academic Motivation, Self-Efficacy and Personality Types of Scheduled Caste Senior Secondary School Students <i>Dr. Nain Singh and Sh. Yudh Veer</i>	228
Consumer Behaviour: How A Consumer Decide to Purchase <i>Ms. Shilpa Batra</i>	238
Survey of Opinion of Student Teachers towards Life Skills in B.Ed. College <i>Mr. Sudarshan L. Patil</i>	244
Towards Decline of Buddhism <i>Dr. Kamal Shankar Srivastava</i>	249
Razia Sultan Under Slave Dynasty <i>Dr. Kamal Shankar Srivastava</i>	264
Jat Race - Origin and Development <i>Dr. Kamal Shankar Srivastava</i>	271
Content and Composition of the Early Upanisads <i>Dr. Kamal Shankar Srivastava</i>	280
Ethics of Warfare in Ancient India <i>Dr. Kamal Shankar Srivastava</i>	291
An Assessment of Tourism Services and Tourist Satisfaction: A Case of Aksum, Tigray, Ethiopia <i>Ato Tesfay Girmay</i>	299
Preliminary Archaeological Investigation in Quiha and the Surrounding Regions in Ethiopia: An Appraisal <i>Ato Tesfay Girmay and Ato Hiruy Danel</i>	306
Knowledge Attitude and Practice of Teacher Educators in Educational Technology in Relation to their Professional Cometency and Satisfaction <i>M. Selvam and M. Vasimalai Raja</i>	328
Academic Achievement in the Context Family and Peer Relations <i>T. Arun Christopher</i>	331
Curriculum Designing and Quality <i>T. Malarkodi</i>	335
Guidelines for Contributors	339

Academic Achievement in the Context Family and Peer Relations

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ABSTRACT

Achievement is not a new term in the society and man since inception to this world is constantly trying to achieve one thing or the other. Family is the building block of every child's life is very important for the balanced growth. During adolescence stage peers also have significant influence on adolescent child. Keeping this in mind, the paper is designed to highlight the link between Family relations and Peer relations and suggest some measures as to enhance positive relationship. The author concludes by saying family and society should realize the fact that improving family relations and peer relations will significantly enhance academic achievement of adolescent child.

Keywords: Academic achievement, family relations, peer relations, adolescent child

INTRODUCTION

Over the past four decades researchers have identified a large number of variables that predict increases in student achievement (e.g., Carroll, 1963; Rosenshine; Squires, Huitt, Segars, 1982; Walberg & Paik, 2000). Achievement is not a new term in the society and man since inception to this world is constantly trying to achieve one thing or the other. From childhood days to adulthood, academic achievement has been an important factor in every student life. Academic achievement is the level of the child's performance in his academics. Performance means how well a child is able to achieve in a given time frame. The performance in academics means familiarity in his school subjects. But students in the adolescent stage are not interested in Academic achievement naturally but only on parents and societies pressure have come to a state where no one can say no to it. It has been deeply rooted into the psyche of every child and their parents. Educationist believes a more holistic approach should prevail (e.g., Chickering & Reisser, 1993; Huitt, 2006) and that efforts of schools should be integrated with other social institutions such as family and community (peers) towards these more holistic ends (Benson, Galbraith & Espeland, 1994).

Hence, this article has been structured on the concept of relationships and does it help in enhancing academic achievement and also suggest some measures to build up positive relationships. It will highlight the influence of family and peer relations on academic achievement of adolescent child.

Academic Achievement

Bloom in his taxonomy on educational objectives has described the importance of cognitive domain development. He feels that for all round development of individual the thinking capacity of the individual has to be enhanced. In other words, systematic and clear thinking is necessary for survival as a person. In Indian condition, to measure the outcome of similar kind of characters in an individual,

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academic achievement tests are conducted. Academic achievement plays a central role in school learning process. It is so important that many students and parents put their heart and soul in enhancing academic achievement among adolescent student. Parents want to send their children to best school possible and provide extra class apart from school especially during their Board exams. This shows the importance given for academic achievement in schools. Academic achievement is influenced by various factors and one such factor is the relationships that exist among students during this stage of adolescence. Vamadevappa (2005) points out parental involvement enhance academic achievement of their wards. Studies show peer relations also influence positives on academic achievement.

Family Relations

Family is the basic building block of the society and it is here from which an individual starts his/her life. The child learns initially everything from the family and it continues to have lasting impression on the child. Family is a source of treasure and strength during adolescent life. But most of the family finds this period of adolescent as a stage of gap between the family and the adolescent child. This is a worrying factor. Family relations are very important for the balanced growth of the individual. During adolescents stage personality is shaped / tuned in the individual and for a positive shaping love and support extended by the family in the psychological sense is essential. Unfortunately due to development of ICT and rapid change in culture, only generation gap is created between parent and adolescent child. Family which happened to be the soul trust for the adolescent gets deteriorated. Many studies reflect on this fact too. But on the contrary, it is well known phenomena that positive family relations will enhance positive feelings and respect for the family which will significantly enhance academic achievement among their wards.

HOW TO CREATE AN ATMOSPHERE OF FRIENDSHIP IN THE FAMILY WITH ADOLESCENT CHILD?

- Talk to the child
- Keep the levels of communication open and clear
- Communications should have empathy and be respected
- Accept feelings of adolescent child
- Develop mutual trust
- Habit of discussion should be part of the family
- Switch off television at-least during dinner time
- Formulation of behaviour codes which have to be respected by both parents and adolescent child
- Respect privacy of adolescent child.
- Positively encourage your child in all the aspects of life.
- Guidance should not be for identification of the mistakes but to sensitize the child about better options to avoid re-occurrence.
- Scheduling study time, play time and entertainment etc.
- Share responsibilities with children
- Never treat adolescent child as miniature adults. Treat them as children.
- If possible provide diverse exposure to the adolescent child like music, dance, arts, literacy activities, philanthropy, sports and games etc.

All these behaviours will strengthen the bond of relationship of the adolescent child which will positively reflect on all the activities of the adolescent.

Peer Relations

As the child grows into adolescent stage he/she starts to learn from the surrounding where he/she is exposed. There is a massive shift in behaviour of the individual. Values and ideals change and new meaning of trust, friendship, peers etc are shaped. As the child grows during this critical stage in his taxonomy, affective domain which talks about the importance of feelings and how attitudes are formed/shaped in individual. According to Bloom (1985), motivation to achieve is influenced by early socialization. Hence, social relations act as an influencing factor for achievement. Peer relations shape peer approval, self-confidence, popularity, peer acceptance, self-esteem, aggression, sacrifice, oneness, sense of pride and loyalty etc.

HOW TO MAXIMIZE BALANCE BETWEEN PEER RELATIONS IN ADOLESCENT CHILD?

- Spending time with children and encourage open conversations.
- Develop a culture of work while you work and play while you play.
- Develop trust between parents and adolescent children about peer groups.
- Allow children to play when they are young and not make them watch television.
- Give freedom to adolescent child and also teach them to be responsible.
- Being role model to your children.
- Never lose temper with the adolescent child while punishing.
- Maintain some rules and regulations at home which are not be broken without valid reasons.
- Share responsibilities with adolescent children
- Invite peer group to home for party, sports & games and for functions and recognize them.
- Accept the uniqueness of every individual as a parent and never impeach ideas on adolescent child.
- As parent maintain good rapport with your child's friends.

CONCLUSION

High academic achievement has become part and parcel of our society and especially for parents who have adolescent child preparing to appear for board exam, I would say, academic achievement is culture to them. That is the craze which is seen in Indian society. The beauty is that this academic achievement will be strengthened when relationships are strong and meaningful. In other words family relations and peer relations play a crucial role in enhancing academic achievement of adolescent child. This message has to be passed on to parents and to a larger extent society so that the student community is blessed.

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